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Business models analysis of Construction Consolidation Centres

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Abstract

The SUCCESS project, financed by the European Union under the H2020 program, aims to contribute to the reduction of negative impacts of the freight distribution caused by the construction sector in urban areas. This technical paper includes some of the results obtained during the project, aiming to improve the current understanding of the functioning of the Construction Consolidation Centres (CCCs). For this purpose, the CANVAS Business Model has been used to assess the business models of several alternatives of CCCs. A CANVAS is a structured methodology that considers nine basic building blocks that cover the main areas of any business. The results obtained from the analysis pointed out that, even though several cities face the similar problems regarding the urban logistics, the level of intensity of these problems vary in each of them. Consequently, the most adequate business models capable of solving each case may also vary. This work will present several CCCs business models proposed by the partners of the SUCCESS project that can be easily adapted to any city aiming to improve its urban logistics

Keywords: Smart Urban Mobility and Logistics, Construction Sector, Construction Consolidation Centres, Urban Transport, Business Model

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1. Introduction and literature review

Urban environments concentrate over 60% (European Commission, 2017a) of population in the European Union generating a dynamic economic activity (85% of the Union's GDP), which requires the transport of a very large amount of goods and people. Urban transport is responsible for 40% of all CO₂ emissions and up to 70% of other pollutants originated from transport (European Commission, 2017a), thus causing poor air quality, and contributing to noise and congestion. For those reasons, urban mobility is one of the main topics to be taken into account in order to define a competitive and efficient transport system. In particular, special attention must be paid to the transportation of goods in urban areas (urban logistics), which represents a significant share of urban traffic. However, urban logistics is often not considered in urban planning even though it is a key element for the sustainable growth and functionality of the cities.

The construction industry accounts for the largest share of the European Union's total energy consumption (40%) and which produces about 35% of all greenhouse gas emissions (European Commission, 2017b). This sector is very fragmented into a large number of suppliers and distributors that deliver their construction materials to the different construction sites around a specific area. Thus, some of the direct consequences of the fragmentation of the construction industry are high transport and production costs and a large number of problems caused by urban freight transport (e.g. noise, air pollution, congestion, etc.). In addition, most of the construction sector's activity is carried out in urban areas, contributing significantly to urban logistics. Consequently, achieving efficient transport of construction materials will also play an important role for the adequate planning of a sustainable urban logistics scheme.

Many initiatives have been proposed over the years intending to improve urban logistics. Among the existing solutions, the use of Urban Consolidation Centres (UCCs) shows a great potential, as pointed out by Browne et al. (2007). The main purpose of UCCs, as defined by these authors, is to avoid the existence of part deliveries of goods into urban areas by consolidating the load in dedicated facilities close to those areas. There are many examples in the literature detailing experiences with the UCCs in different cities and sectors. Even though a detailed literature review of the results obtained pilot or commercial experiences is out of the scope of this paper, a brief summary of some of them can give an exact idea of the importance of the Urban Logistics concept. In a very comprehensive review of the use of UCCs, Browne et al. (2005) identifies 67 examples and classifies them in groups by country and category (where 26 correspond to research initiatives, 13 are pilots and 28 are fully operational). In a more recent work, Allen et al. (2012) analyses the trend on the number of UCCs implemented worldwide from 1970 to 2010 and identifies more than one hundred experiences all over the world. The analysis shows a clearly growing trend over the years on the use of UCCs as a potential solution for urban logistics. Other examples of successfully UCCs implemented later than 2010 are those included in the SMILE project and presented by Navarro et al. (2016), or the initiatives under the CITYLAB European project (2017).

However, there are many experiences where the activity of a UCC stops when the support from public authorities ends. For example, only 27 from the 67 UCCs identified by Browne et al. (2005) were still operating at the moment of the elaboration of their report. In a more recent work, Ville et al. (2013) indicated that only 20 UCCs of genuinely significant consolidation terminals survived without subsidies from municipalities from an initial number of more than one hundred initiatives. For that reason, it is very important to analyse the future feasibility of the UCC prior to the start of its activities. Many authors have proposed different theoretical approaches with that objective. Kin et al. (2017) applied social cost-benefit analyses (SCBA) on a UCC in the Belgian city of Antwerp and concluded that, even though the studied UCC has a positive impact upon the society and environment, it did not yield a net societal benefit at its state. Other authors such as Lewis (2010) and Van Duin et al. (2007) also used CBA for the analysis of existing experiences. There are also several works in which modelling techniques have been used in order to obtain conclusions. For example, Faure et al. (2016) analysed the influence of the urban morphology on the future viability of the UCC by checking the results obtained from modelling while considering circular, rectangular and elliptical shapes. They conclude that, even though the morphology plays a role on the UCC viability, many indirect parameters should also be taken into account. Roca-Riu and Estrada (2012) proposed a model that allows the evaluation of the potential benefits obtained if a Consolidation Centre is used. The model applied to a case study in L'Hospitalet del Llobregat estimates that a 40% of transport companies should be committed to the collaboration strategy to cover the CC costs.

The choice of an appropriate business model is a key factor for the success or failure of any initiative (Faure et al., 2016) and, consequently, it is very important to define the best option for every particular case. Quark et al. (2014) proposed the development of adequate business models through the use of CANVAS methodology in order to analyse the long term potential of the proposed solutions. These authors analysed using this approach Bentobox, a solution applicable to both home delivery and business deliveries capable of de-synchronizing the delivery process. Their analysis showed that one of the main challenges to overcome was the adequate identification of the right customers as well as the right governance model in the case where more than one logistic operator or party will use the proposed solution. CANVAS models were also used in the framework of the TURBLOG project (2011) in order to identify the most suitable business models based on each logistic profile of the initiative. In addition, in the work carried out in the TURBLOG a very important building block was added to the original CANVAS methodology, the externalities, to take into account the value proposition to society.

The construction sector has been identified as one of the sectors with more potential for the use of UCCs. Browne et al. 2011, used their proposed evaluation framework in order to identify major construction sites as one of the location types where the use of UCCs are most likely to succeed. Allen et al. (2014) studied six UCC schemes established in Europe in recent years including two Construction Consolidation Centres (CCCs). The authors found that the level of demand and the sharing of UCC costs and benefits between the various supply chain parties involved are two critical factors for the success of a UCC. They also pointed out that these factors can be easily addressed for CCCs. A success story of special interest is the case of the use of CCCs in London, proved successfully in the construction of Heathrow Terminal 5 and the London Olympics developments, which has finally lead to an existing and operative network of CCCs in the city (London 2017). Due to the potential of CCCs, the identification of an adequate business model specific to this sector is of special interest. This technical paper includes some of the results obtained during the project, aiming to improve the current understanding of the functioning of the Construction Consolidation Centres (CCCs). For this purpose, the CANVAS Business Model has been used to assess the business models of several CCC alternatives .

2. SUCCESS project

SUCCESS – Sustainable Urban Consolidation Centres for construction is a project financed by the European Union under the H2020 Programme. The main aim of SUCCESS is to reduce the negative impacts of freight distribution of the construction sector in urban areas. In order to do so, the project focuses on to what extent and how the Supply Chain Management and Construction Consolidation Centres concepts could bring about tested and replicable solutions (adequate collaborative frameworks and, as a result, sustainable business models) to address problems in the construction supply chains, focusing on distribution networks, construction sites and reverse logistics.

SUCCESS addresses the feasibility of optimising the supply chain through the use of Construction Consolidation Centres in urban areas, also developing best practices and guidance on innovative an approach that integrates knowledge, competences of research institutes, public authorities and business operators.

The general objectives of the SUCCESS project are:

- to decrease the negative externalities produced by urban freight transportation from the construction sector: congestion, pollution, noise and accidents;
- to improve the overall quality of life in urban zones;
- to improve the use of the existing transport infrastructures and to diminish their degradation, so to decrease building and renovating costs and impacts on urban environment;
- to increase the level of cooperation and coordination among all the stakeholders of the supply chain as well as policy makers (Construction Companies, Supply Chain Actors, Transportation Companies, Public Administrations,...) for reduced transport impacts on society;
- to develop reusable methods and tools which can be adopted for the CCC implementation and for the optimisation of the construction sites, distribution network, and reverse logistics activities.

SUCCESS has the following specific goals, which are related directly to the beneficiaries of the project, i.e. public administrations and private companies:

- to improve the current situation of Construction Logistics in urban areas, from an operative and economic point of view with application in four sites: Luxemburg, Paris, Valencia and Verona, all located in urban areas with high congestion, urban density and strict environmental constraints;
- to gather relevant data from construction sites in the Pilot cities, to design optimised solutions to elaborate on them and then validate the results with the direct involvement of policy makers and business players;

- to understand the implication of the use of Construction Consolidation Centres and their impact on construction sites (the avoidance of loss of materials, a better use of time and space allowing an easier implementation of a just-in-time company policy), on the distribution network and on reverse logistics (the maximisation of the load factor, the decrease if the number of vehicles and kilometres travelled by them);
- to supply with relevant information to the policy makers (city, local and regional authorities) and cooperate with them to shape policies which take into consideration supply chain requirements;
- to improve the management of construction sites, minimising the non-valued activities;
- to formulate a reliable and sustainable business model to be used in the field of Construction Logistics in urban areas, concerning the use of CCCs, the use of Optimisation and ICT tools, and the cooperation among the involved stakeholders;
- to assess the replicability of the solutions proposed in other European cities and to compare them with the state of the art in the USA;
- to spread at both European as well as international level the business models and solutions developed and tested in the project considering supply chain collaborative approaches and the use of CCCs.

The main results expected to be obtained from the project are listed below:

1. AS-IS Analysis of the current situation of four pilot sites by collecting information and data in order to detect problems, inefficiencies and potential improvements to the Construction Supply Chain.
2. Best Practice Guide offering solutions and optimisation tools for the Construction Supply Chain (e.g. RFID and GIS technologies, e-collaboration tools, process mapping, business models, etc.).
3. Definition and simulation of several scenarios through the development of adequate algorithms and tools. The evaluation of the results will permit the assessment of the most convenient potential solutions to be applied.
4. “Business model” evaluation based on construction sites’ results in order to ensure replicability of the solutions developed, especially in other European cities.

This paper shows the results obtained in the framework of the SUCCES project, where several business models for the implementation of CCCs in urban areas have been assessed by analysing the cooperation and coordination of the Supply Chain stakeholders from three different perspectives: economic, commercial and organisational points of view. For this purpose, a general methodology for Business Model analysis has been selected and applied to four pilot sites in: Paris, Luxemburg, Verona and Valencia. In order to do so the CANVAS model has been selected as the most suitable tool to analyse several Business Models for each of the four aforementioned cities.

3. Business models for CCCs in cities

3.1. The CANVAS model

The concept of business model became popular in the 1990s in the IT sector, mainly used by dotcom companies during its search for investors. Currently, the concept has become widespread to practically all the sectors in the industry and has focused more attention on the academic world. Many authors have provided alternative definitions of what a business model is. For example, Shafer et al. (2005) mentioned 12 authors that have offered alternative definitions, and also proposed their own based on the definition of the words included in the term (business and model).

Different methods can be found in the literature to either identify the existing business model of an already created company (mainly for software development purposes) or as an assistant tool to identify the most convenient structure to be adopted by a starting company. Even though these methods provide a quite comprehensive view of the complete structure and operative of a business and could be used during the definition stage of the business (before the actual start of activities), the degree of detail involved in their development makes its use more appropriate for later uses. Much simpler approaches are required for the conceptual design of a future activity, which is actually the definition of the fundamental structure that will define the future activity of the company. In this sense, the Business Model Canvas (BCM) dominates most of the dedicated literature.

Osterwalder (2010) states as the goal of any Business Model the description of the “rationale of how an organization creates, delivers and captures value”. The Business Model Canvas (BMC) consists on a strategic management and entrepreneurial tool that uses a visual chart/template to describe the structure of a business plan.

The BMC can be printed out onto a large surface so that groups of people can formulate ideas and discuss business model elements together, using pens and post-it notes amongst other implementing tools. Its hands-on approach makes it ideal for business model understanding, discussion, creativity and analysis.

BMC has a structured methodology to describe any business through the systematic description of nine basic building blocks that show the logic of how a company intends to make money. The nine blocks cover the four main areas of a business: customers, offer, infrastructure, and financial viability. The contents of the nine blocks are identified from a series of questions, which should be answered by the promoters of the business, and they are graphically represented using a predefined template. The following Figure shows the main structure of the BCM.

Fig. 1 Template used in the methodology Business Model Canvas

3.2. Results from the SUCCES project

SUCCESS project targeted the construction industry as a sector with a major impact on urban environments and aims, in particular, to assess the impact of the CCCs introduction in the construction supply chain. For the matter, the project proposed a framework for the assessment of CCCs in pursuit of more resource-efficient, environmentally-friendly and safer logistics operations for the construction industry.

The methodology followed to analyse different CCCs business models in the four countries participating in the SUCCESS project was as follows: firstly, a working group was created in each city composed by the country partnership that counts with the participation of construction companies, research centres and municipalities. Each working group analysed the city characteristics that influence on the urban logistic and, more specifically, the construction supply chain. In particular, a SWOT analysis per city was performed to identify the most relevant problems and opportunities for a CCC implementation.

Afterwards, at least two different scenarios were proposed by the city pilots in order to assess the related business models using the CANVAS methodology. The set of scenarios proposed by each working group include: scenario a) a CCC operated by a construction company for all its construction sites in the same area; scenario b) a CCC operated by an external private operator for several construction sites of different construction companies; scenario c) a CCC operated by a public-private partnership for several constructions sites of different construction

companies and finally; scenario d) a CCC built on a temporary basis by a construction company for a building development in a specific area. The following figure illustrates schematically the different scenarios proposed for the assessment of the business models:

Fig. 2 Scenarios proposed for the implementation of a CCC

After the definition of the scenarios for the CCCs in each of the city pilots of the SUCCESS project, the business models were analysed using the CANVAS methodology. The assessment of the business models with the CANVAS methodology show that, in general, there were two different business models identified from the point of view of the construction company. On the one hand, the business model of a CCC operated by the construction company as a cost centre, where the main benefits come from the optimisation and the savings in the core operations of the construction company (i.e. construction activity). On the other hand, the business model of a CCC operated by an external operator (public or private) that is managed as a profit centre and in which the revenues come from services provided to the companies of the construction industry. The following figure summarises the common sections of the CANVAS that both business models have in common, where highlighted in grey are the ones that present differences.

Fig. 3. Common sections of BMC for a CCC business model from the point of view of the construction company

As shown in the figure 3, common aspects for both Business Cases are as follows:

- The project SUCCESS carried out a set of questionnaires to the different stakeholders of the construction industry to gather their opinion in CCC implementation. The identified key partners obtained from this work were:

Partner	Role
Material Supplier	Constant and efficient relationships with the CCC staff to reach high levels of performance regarding the logistics system
Construction Companies	Operator of the CCC when the construction company manages the CCC. Clients of the CCC when the CCC is managed by an external logistics operator
Trade Contractors	Close relationship with the CCC for the coordination of their operations on site
Public Authorities	Promotion of policies to foster more sustainable urban logistics and the use of Urban Consolidation Centres

- The key activities of a CCC include:
 - Just in Time material deliveries to the construction site in order to reduce the stock volume on site and improving the performance of the site operations.
 - Route and Load factor optimization and Cargo consolidation: these are the key activities to be performed by the CCC operator because they can potentially optimise the transport flows. The reduction of the number of empty trips, the non-fully loaded vehicles, the achievement of higher load factor rates and the route optimization allows the CCC operator to save the total distance in tonnes or cubic meters per kilometre covered.
 - The CCC operator manages the materials' inventory of the CCC with the suppliers in order to meet with the demand from the construction sites.

- Reverse logistics management: the CCC manages the material returning from the construction sites (theft, unused, damaged or waste materials) to the final destination (reuse in other construction site or waste deposits).
- The common key resources in both Business Models of a CCC are the following:
 - Warehousing: Warehouse facility to perform the required logistics operations needed for supplying the different construction sites served through the CCC. The facility has to be planed and sized according to the construction sites' requirements during the test life-cycle in order to be able to evaluate results.
 - Handling equipment: in the same manner than the warehousing, the handling equipment needed for the logistics operations has to be sized according to the demand requirements.
 - Vehicle fleet that has to be optimized according to the transport needs and characteristics. However, the fleet can be composed by a mix of owned vehicles, rented vehicles and subcontracted vehicles that help to meet with the peaks of transport demand.
 - Optimisation and management software: The optimisation software for the route calculation and material consolidation is a key element for the CCC's operations. This software allows the CCC to optimise the transport operations and achieve the required potential savings.
- The common value proposition aspects of the CANVAS business model in the CCC are listed below:
 - Increases the level of performance on site due to JIT deliveries, stock reduction and better supply chain management.
 - Increase the global efficiency on the logistics processes due to better management of the transport flows, optimisation of the routes, load factors or fewer operations on site.
 - Reduce the congestion on site due to fewer trucks and less volume of material storage.
 - Better delivery process on the construction site increasing reliability, flexibility, traceability and JIT deliveries of the delivery process.
 - Positive environmental impacts: reduction of the negative emissions, noise and congestion in urban areas that improve the quality of life of the citizens.
- The common channels identified to communicate and reach the CCCs customers in both Business Models include, on one side, direct contact, website, mailing and phone calls for awareness rising and on the other side, tailored studies, control reports, meetings and direct contact for the daily management with the CCCs clients.

The following table shows a comparison of the different aspects of the Canvas Business Models between a CCC operated by a construction company (CCC as a Cost Centre) and the CCC operated by an external company (CCC as a Profit Centre):

	Business Model 1 (CCC as a Cost Centre)	Business Model 2 (CCC as a Profit Centre)
Customer Segment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Construction Companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Construction Companies ▪ Trade contractors ▪ Suppliers ▪ Transport Companies ▪ Public Authorities
Customer Relationship 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The Construction Company is the owner and customer of the CCC. Relation between different departments of the same company. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The CCC operator is the service provider meanwhile the construction companies or trade contractors are the clients.
Cost Structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Facility ▪ Labor Force ▪ Equipment ▪ Vehicle Fleet ▪ Others... 	Cost of the contracted services : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Storage ▪ Repack of materials ▪ Reverse logistics ▪ Others...

<p>Revenue Streams</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Savings due to higher operations performance, less material theft, wasted or damaged. ▪ Higher profit margins due to more supply chain control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Savings due to higher operations performance, less material theft, wasted or damaged.
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Fig. 4. Main differences of the BMC for a CCC business model from the point of view of the construction company

In the Business Model 1, the CCC is operated as a cost centre by the construction company (although its operations could be outsourced), the business model from the construction company’s point of view allows it to optimise their site operations thanks to the benefits of the CCC (e.g. Just-In-Time deliveries, higher reliability, labor performance improvement, etc.). The core business of the construction activity and the cost structure of this Business Model is composed among others, by the cost of the facility, the fleet, the labor of the CCC and other investments required for the daily operations. The revenue streams also come from the core business in terms of savings and performance improvement of the construction activity. Regarding the customer segment and its relationships, this business model of the CCC is focused on the construction industry; nevertheless, the daily operations of the facility could be outsourced to specialised logistics operators. The main characteristics of this Business Model make this case more appropriate for CCCs that only operate for a single construction company (serving one or more sites) and that could operate both on a temporary or on a permanent basis. Moreover, its simpler operative makes this business model of CCC more likely to be implemented in specially constrained projects in all kind of cities.

In the Business Model 2, the CCC operates as a profit centre managed and operated by an external logistics operator and the construction company contracts the services offered (e.g. delivery management, storage, material repacking, etc.). The construction company pays for the CCC services, thus the payments correspond to the cost structure of the BMC from the point of view of the construction company, which benefits in terms of cost savings in the construction activity thanks to CCC operations (revenue streams). In this business case, the fewer control of the supply chain, thus less potential savings compared to the previous one, and the payment for the CCC services makes this business model less profitable for the construction company but also less risky than the first one. As an external logistics operator manages the CCC and the construction company is the client, this CCC can work for several companies and trade contractors, and it is recommended to work on permanent basis with several clients in order to benefit from economies of scale. In addition, the analysis carried out also pointed out that this business model seems more appropriated for highly constrained urban areas that need long term holistic solutions. Finally, the possible involvement of the Public Authorities supporting this business model is easier than in the first one because it comprises several companies of the construction industry.

4. Conclusions

The use of the CANVAS methodology has allowed the identification of the most feasible business models for CCCs. This has been the result of a Working Group participated by construction companies, research centres and municipalities, and has identified two suitable solutions. In one of them, the CCC functions as a Cost Centre where the Construction Company is the owner and customer of the CCC, whereas in the other, the CCC acts as a Profit Centre and it is operated by a service provider meanwhile the construction companies or trade contractors are the clients. Both approaches share the same key partners, key activities, key resources, value propositions and channels, although they show important difference regarding their business drivers. In the first approach, the Construction Company retains the total control of the whole process, and the CCC acts as a solution capable of improving its operations on site. In this specific case, the CCC management is easier due to the fewer number of stakeholders involved meanwhile the potential benefits are limited to the activity of one construction company. The main driver of this option is the logistics efficiency and the operations of the Construction Company and consequently, even if transport and logistics savings are achieved, the possibility of its promotion through the implementation of policies promoted by public authorities is more restricted. In the second approach, the entry of a new neutral actor (i.e. the logistics operator) in the construction supply chain allows to open the solution to different construction companies and to obtain benefits from economies of scale, being able to put the focus on the global transport and logistics savings that minimise the negative impact of construction activities in the cities. The CCC management is more complicated due to the higher number of clients and the Construction Company losses some control, but the CCC operation is significantly simpler from the point of view of the company. This approach requires more coordination between the different stakeholders and seems to be more adequate in high-congested areas that face important urban logistics problems. In this regard, the promotion by public authorities is

easier to justify and plays a fundamental role by developing actions to facilitate the operation of the service provider and to reach the number of companies that make profitable the CCC operations.

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